

“Modern methods and approaches in English language”

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Abstract;The article dicusses the possibilities of using modern methods and approaches in the process of teaching English a forean language.

KEY WORDS; communicative language teaching intensive learning method ,task based learning method,variety modern skills.

Introduction

The rapid development of modern society forces the studentto quickly learn and understand the material,especially a foreinlanguage.Nowadays,mastering at least one foreign language is becoming an indispensable requirement for the professional qualification of a specialist .Therefore it is necessary to pay attention to the efficiensy and quality of the process of learning foreign language.The most effective method of language learning are interactive method .The purpose of this article is to determine the main role of interactive methods in teaching English .To achive the goal the following tasks were defined;to describe the main interactive method and to give examples of the use of these methods.

The term ”interactive”refers to people working together and influencing each other .This situation implies a dialogue on conversation.Therefore;these methods are focused on the interaction between students and the teachers,as well as only between students.This requires the active role of students in the learning process.

Interactive methods are the so-called group thinking ,that is methods of pedagogical influence which are part of educational content.One of unique features of interactive methods is that they are carried out in a corporation with the teachers and students,through joint activities.The goal of interactive educational is to create special conditions that lead to the involment of all stidents in the learning process,in which partisipitians understand and aware of everything that happening,influence each other and contribute can add establish friendly and mutually beneficial relations .The most popular method are role-playing games ,brainstorming ,case - study method ,prethentation and discussion.They develop communicative skills logical thinking and various types of intellectual activities such as particulary well-

suitable for engaging students more actively in acquiring knowledge skills and strategies.

The modern age requires a new approach, new methods of teaching foreign languages. Awakening a child's desire to learn, master new knowledge and activities in the meantime, build a further direction of their own education is the main goal of the current school. The students are given the task of independently studying, finding, analyzing materials, while the main task of the teacher is the right direction. The teacher needs to logically competently construct a lesson so that students are interested in learning English, since the practice of the traditional method, forcing students to cram words; grammar in practice did not give the desired result. The search for new teaching methods is associated with a lack of motivation among students to learn English. Very often, there is no positive motivation, since when learning a foreign language, students encounter some difficulties and do not absorb the material due to their psychological characteristics. Experiences show that the use of various, modern, fresh sources and means provokes students' interest, increases their motivation to study.

The goal of these approaches and methods is to master a living, spoken language and to learn the ability to communicate. When using the communicative methods in teaching, students are more active. The task of the teacher in this case is the ability to involve everyone in the audience in the conversation. The essence of this method is to create real communication situations. When recreating the dialogue, the student has the opportunity to put into practice all the knowledge gained. An important advantage of the method is that it has a variety of tasks: role-plays, discussions, debates, etc. According to Willis (1996), there are six types of tasks:

- > Listing tasks: For example, students might have to make up a list of things they would pack if they were going on a beach vacation.
- > Sorting and ordering: Students work in pairs and make up a list of the most important characteristics of an ideal vacation.
- > Comparing: Students compare ads for two different supermarkets.

- > Problem-solving: Students read a letter to an advice columnist and suggest a solution to the writer's problems.
- > Sharing personal experience: Students discuss their reactions to an ethical or moral dilemma.
- > Creative tasks: Students prepare plans for redecorating a house.

Teaching methods are the process of interaction between the teacher and students, as a result of which there is a transfer and assimilation of knowledge, skills and abilities provided by the content of training. It should be noted that the teaching method is a complex, systemic formation, which is characterized by all the characteristics that underlie the classification. The combination of different forms of work and methods helps to creatively organize the lesson, arousing the interest of students in the subjects.

The process of English communication learning will be more student-centered but less time consuming. Therefore, it promises that the teaching quality will be improved and students' applied English communication can be effectively cultivated, meaning that students' communicative competence will be further developed. Language in education would ideally and ordinarily build on such naturally acquired language ability, enriching it through the development of literacy into an instrument for abstract thought and the acquisition of academic knowledge. Teachers use a range of local texts or English translation of literature in the classroom. The use of language as well as the use of a variety of accents in listening activities or tests is encouraged in the English language

classroom. With the proliferation of tablets and smart phones, it is believed that textbooks will disappear in a few years and students' applied English communication can be effectively cultivated, meaning that students' communicative competence will be further developed. Language in education

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Teaching methodology is a complex of sciences that study the methods of orderly interconnected activities of the teacher and students, aimed at solving educational problems, a system of purposeful teacher actions that organize the educational activities of students leading to the achievement of learning goals. The methodology includes teaching methods, which include the following types: traditional, innovative, etc.

Methodology in science appears, in fact, depending on the requirements of the time. In the traditional, traditional «grammar-translation» method of teaching foreign languages, the main goal of the learning process was to make the student understand the structure of the language and the meaning of the read text through

translation. Teaching how to speak and write a foreign language was often neglected. When teaching grammar in a communicative way, it is recommended to demonstrate and teach the classic grammatical units and sentences by repeating them and using them in practice. In doing so, the student does not even feel that he is learning heavy grammatical material. Grammatical concepts and lengthy explanations of rules hinder the development of a student's communication skills. As it is known, the child begins to learn communicative skills in his mother tongue first from the habit of listening. A child who has not yet «finished speaking» can listen and understand what parents or other people are saying. That is why teaching a foreign language in a communicative way begins with mastering the habit of listening. Methodologists emphasize that it is necessary to spend more time in the beginning to develop the habit of listening, and to give more listening activities.

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